

CONSIDERATIONS FOR APPLICATION OF RF-OVER-FIBER TO NAVY SYSTEMS

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Introduction

The superior distance-bandwidth product of optical fiber communications has led to the development of a wide array of active and passive optical/optoelectronic components for the digital data communication industry. The cable television (CATV) industry has been the primary driver for development of high performance analog fiber optic links. RF-over-fiber offers advantages for military RF signal distribution, primarily antenna remoting, as such there is significant interest in leveraging the commercial developments noted above for these military applications. Because the link distances for many of these military applications are often so short that the RF performance is poorer than a design using copper coax or waveguide, the adoption of RF-over-fiber in deployed systems has been limited. This has motivated continuing development of link components and designs to improve link performance [1-5]. This paper will summarize system-level metrics relevant to Navy antenna remoting applications, discuss an example deployed system, and conclude with an update on recent improvements in analog link components/performance.

Antenna Remoting System Metrics

Some key metrics that are common for many military antenna remoting applications are: 1) RF performance (NF, SFDR, bandwidth, isolation); 2) Size, weight, and power (at the antenna end of link, the receiver end of the link, and the cable plant); 3) System reconfiguration/flexibility; 4) Reliability/maintainability; and 5) Cost. Copper coax/waveguide distribution must compensate for frequency dependent loss. The proximity of high power transmit transition lines with high sensitivity receive lines makes RF isolation an issue. The multitude of RF links on military platforms make the size of the cable plant a significant issue for avionic, submarine, and even surface ship applications; weight is critical in the case of avionics applications. Installation/routing of stiff copper coax and waveguide in confined spaces is also an issue. Particular copper coax and waveguides are installed based on the frequencies transmitted by the systems involved. Thus system reconfiguration involving replacing or adding new RF sensors requires modification or addition to the cable plant. In the case of RF-over-fiber, frequency dependence is relatively weak; isolation between fibers and from fiber to copper coax is high; the cable plant size and weight is low and the flexibility of cables is high; system reconfiguration can be done without modifying the cable plant as the same optical fiber is used no matter the frequency of the RF signal being transmitted. Though each application/design must be evaluated independently, RF bandwidth, RF isolation of cables, size and weight of the cable plant, and system reconfiguration/flexibility are metrics that often favor an RF-over-fiber design, and the remaining metrics noted above often favor the copper coax design.

In contrast to commercial applications where the distance-bandwidth product is typically the motivation for an optical link approach, for many military RF signal distribution applications these other metrics noted above may be the motivation for the RF-over-fiber design, and it is left as a challenge to match the NF and SFDR performance of the copper transport solution. For example, an LNA - balance photonic link cascade with wide band operation up to approximately 18 GHz, NF=6dB, and SFDR=115 dB^{2/3} can be built with currently available components. For cable segments up to approximately 20 meters an LNA – copper coax design can match this RF performance, but for longer distances, loss will result in degraded RF performance at high frequency. Calculations comparing the RF performance of LNA - photonic link cascades and LNA-copper coax cascades for various photonic link designs and coax cables, over a range of distances and frequencies relevant to Navy applications, will be presented.

Example Navy Systems

An example of a successfully deployed RF-over-fiber system is the GPS Fiber Optic Antenna Link (FOAL). FOAL provides GPS satellite signals to the Navigation Sensor System Interface (NAVSSI) GPS receiver aboard Navy surface ships via an optical link between the mast-mounted antenna and the internally-mounted GPS receiver, and is now deployed on approximately 100 ships. The motivation for FOAL is RF isolation and a more flexible cable for routing. The RF photonic link met the NF and SFDR requirement which were determined by GPS receiver characteristics, making moot the fact LD4-50A Heliac, which would otherwise be used for this application would reduce the requirements of the front end LNA and/or provide a link with improved dynamic range [5]. The FOAL antenna assembly (AN-3819D/SRN) consists of a dual band (L1, L2) GPS patch antenna connected to a high gain filter/amplifier and a directly modulated diode laser transmitter modified from a commercially available module designed for CATV and cell phone antenna remoting. The FOAL receiver module (OE-553/U) houses an optical receiver which is also a modified commercial unit. The system is redundant, including two antennas and two receivers; an optical splitter and switch in each receiver module allows for either receiver to connect to either antenna. Though this system is relatively simple in that it employs a commercially proven directly modulated sub-octave link, it serves to demonstrate that single-mode fiber RF photonic links can be reliably applied to fleet-deployed, mission critical systems.

SSC-SD is currently investigating applications of RF-over-fiber to additional military systems including a submarine mast wherein transmission of a collection of wideband RF and high-speed digital signals through a rotational interface is required. The design of the RF rotary joint is a significant challenge. Transmission of selected signals via WDM in combination with a single channel fiber optic rotary joint can simplify the RF rotary joint design making it possible to transmit all desired signals from the rotating platform to inboard. These systems will be summarized in the conference presentation.

Conclusion

Wider adoption of RF-over-fiber for military application depends on continued advances in modulator efficiency, high-power high-speed photodetectors, power efficient low RIN sources, and link designs providing significant improvement in linearity. Improving photonic link NF to ultimately remove the need for a front end LNA offers wideband passive front end antenna remoting designs. Recent work performed under SSC-SD contract towards these goals, including demonstration of NF < 7 dB without an LNA over 6-12 GHz, will be summarized [6].

References

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